

Studies of Coordination Compounds of Cadmium(II) and Zinc(II) with L-Amino Acids as Primary Ligands and Vitamin B₆ (Pyridoxine) as Secondary Ligand : A Polarographic Approach

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Polarographic technique has been used to determine the mixed ligand complex formation between Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} with L-tyrosine, L-arginine, L-methionine, L-hydroxytryptophane, L-tryptophane, L-hydroxyproline, L-proline and L-histidine as primary ligands and vitamin B₆ as a secondary ligands. Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} formed 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes. The stability trend of the complexes have been explained on the basis of bonding, basicity and steric hindrance,

Amino acids and their compounds with different metal ions play important role in biology, pharmacy and industry¹. Vitamin B₆ also has an important role in plants, animals and human being. Therefore, the study of its compounds has great importance³. A survey of literature reveals no reference so far regarding the ternary complexes of Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} with amino acids and vitamin B₆, studied polarographically. Therefore, the authors have undertaken the present study.

Results and Discussion

Cd^{II} gave a well-defined two-electron reversible reduction and diffusion-controlled wave in 1.0 M KNO₃ at pH 8.50 ± 0.01 (Ref. 3), the value of $E_{1/2}$ being -0.586 V vs SCE. The nature of waves is also reversible. The Zn^{II} gave a well-defined two-electron quasi-reversible reduction wave in 1.0 M NaClO₄ at pH 8.50 ± 0.01 at 25°. The value of $E_{1/2}$ quasi-reversible of Zn²⁺ was -1.010 V vs SCE which by Gellings method⁴ gave $(E_{1/2})_{rev.} = -0.989$ V. In all the cases, the irreversibility increased with increase in concentration of ligands.

Vitamin B₆ binary complexes : Cd^{II} formed 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with vitamin B₆ in the concentration range 50–200 mM as confirmed by the Lingane method⁵. The values of stability constants were log β₀₁ = 1.45 and log β₀₂ = 2.32 respectively. In case of Zn^{II}, the concentration of ligand varied from 50 to 250 mM and current voltage curves were drawn. The value of $E_{1/2}$ increased with increase in concentration of ligand. The $(E_{1/2})_{rev.}$ values were calculated by modified Gellings method by plotting $E - RT/nF \log (i_{\infty} - i)/i$ against i to zero current value. Lingane method⁵ revealed the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes of Zn^{II} with vitamin B₆ having stability constants log β₀₁ = 1.72 and log β₀₂ = 2.93 respectively.

L-Amino acid binary complexes : The free ligand concentrations of L-amino acids were calculated from pK₂^H and pH (8.50 ± 0.01) values. In case of Zn^{II}, the $(E_{1/2})_{rev.}$ values were calculated using modified Gellings method. The method of DeFord and Hume⁶ modified by Irving⁷

revealed the formation of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes of Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} with selected L-amino acids. The values of stability constant are given in Table 2.

L-Amino acid-vitamin B₆ ternary system : This system has been studied at pH 8.50 ± 0.01 at 25°. The value of $E_{1/2}$ increased in concentration of vitamin B₆ to the binary system showing ternary complex formation. In case of Zn^{II}, the $(E_{1/2})_{rev.}$ values were calculated by modified Gellings method. For the calculation of log β₁₁ and log β₁₂, the studies were carried out at two different concentrations of vitamin B₆ at 0.025 and 0.05 M while varying the concentration of L-amino acidate from 0.5 to 50 mM, and cur-

Fig. 1. Cadmium-L-tyrosinate-vitamin B₆ system.

rent-voltage curves were drawn. The nature of waves in case of the Cd^{II} complexes were reversible, while that in case of Zn^{II}, irreversibility increased with increase in concentrations of ligands. Schaap and McMaster⁸ method confirmed the formation of 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes in case of both the metals ions. The system $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ data and the plots between $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ vs $[X]$, where $X = L$ -

TABLE 1—pK VALUES AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES OF Cd^{II} WITH L-AMINO ACIDS AND VITAMIN B₆

μ = 1.0 M KNO₃, pH = 8.50 ± 0.01, Temp. = 25°

Ligand	pK _a ^H	log β ₀₁	log β ₀₂	log β ₁₀	log β ₂₀	log β ₃₀	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁
L-Tyrosine	9.11	—	—	3.54	6.11	9.00	4.32	6.85	9.71
L-Arginine	9.10	—	—	3.60	6.30	9.11	4.40	7.01	10.00
L-Methionine	9.20	—	—	3.69	7.00	9.23	4.43	7.39	10.21
L-Hydroxytryptophane	9.32	—	—	3.75	7.40	9.41	4.60	7.93	10.30
L-Tryptophane	9.40	—	—	4.45	7.52	9.92	4.66	7.92	10.53
L-Hydroxyproline	10.20	—	—	4.62	8.21	11.11	4.80	8.61	11.72
L-Proline	10.60	—	—	4.70	8.72	11.80	5.20	9.32	12.32
L-Histidine	9.20	—	—	5.40	9.67	12.00	6.13	10.42	12.84
Vitamin B ₆	—	1.45	2.32	—	—	—	—	—	—

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND DERIVED DATA FOR Cd AND Zn-L-TYROSINATE-VITAMIN B₆ SYSTEMS

[Cd^{II}] = 0.5 mM, μ = 1.0 M KNO₃, pH = 8.50 ± 0.01

Temp. = 25°, Vitamin B₆ = 0.025 M (Fixed)

[Zn^{II}] = 0.5 mM, μ = 1.0 M, NaClO₄, pH = 8.50 ± 0.01

Temp. = 25°, Vitamin B₆ = 0.025 M (Fixed)

[L-Tyr.] M	F ₀₀ [X,Y]	F ₁₀ [X,Y] ×10 ⁻⁴	F ₂₀ [X,Y] ×10 ⁻⁸	F ₃₀ [X,Y] ×10 ⁻⁹	F ₀₀ [X,Y] ×10 ⁻²	F ₁₀ [X,Y] ×10 ⁻⁶	F ₂₀ [X,Y] ×10 ⁻⁹	F ₃₀ [X,Y] ×10 ⁻¹¹
0.00	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.0005	38.77	7.38	1.30	1.00	14.06	2.80	5.24	1.00
0.001	141.68	13.98	1.31	1.00	54.81	5.47	5.29	1.00
0.002	548.41	27.32	1.32	1.00	279.48	10.97	5.39	1.01
0.003	1 228.07	40.87	1.33	1.01	499.80	16.65	5.49	1.01
0.004	2 186.08	54.60	1.34	1.00	902.06	22.55	5.59	1.00
0.005	3 431.66	68.59	1.35	1.00	1 433.24	28.66	5.69	1.01
0.006	4 963.05	82.68	1.36	1.02	2 095.78	34.92	5.79	1.00
0.008	8 927.26	111.56	1.38	1.00	3 848.26	48.10	5.98	0.99
0.010	14 127.69	141.25	1.40	1.00	6 269.96	62.09	6.19	1.00
0.020	60 412.36	302.05	1.50	1.00	28 805.91	144.02	7.19	1.00
0.030	1 44 618.83	482.05	1.60	1.01	73 766.86	245.88	8.19	1.00
0.040	2 72 986.10	682.46	1.70	1.00	1 47 115.82	367.78	9.19	1.00
0.050	4 51 434.17	902.86	1.80	1.00	2 54 866.77	509.68	10.19	1.00

log A = 0.262, log B = 3.926, log C = 8.115, log D = 9.00

log A = 0.47, log B = 5.71, log C = 9.84, log D = 11.04

*The data and plots for [Cd-L-aminoacidate], [Zn-L-amino acidate], [Cd-L-tyrosinate-vitamin B₆], [Zn-L-tyrosinate-vitamin B₆] at [vitamin B₆] = 0.05 M (fixed) and rest of ternary systems can be obtained from author on request.

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES OF Zn^{II} WITH L-AMINO ACIDS AND VITAMIN B₆

μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄, pH = 8.50 ± 0.01 Temp. = 25°

Ligands	log β ₀₁	log β ₀₂	log β ₁₀	log β ₂₀	log β ₃₀	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁
L-Tyrosine	—	—	4.15	8.28	11.00	4.30	8.45	11.30
L-Arginine	—	—	4.23	8.30	11.23	4.40	8.60	11.45
L-Methionine	—	—	4.38	8.36	11.73	4.52	8.72	11.92
L-Hydroxytryptophane	—	—	4.50	8.72	12.00	4.70	8.85	12.32
L-Tryptophane	—	—	5.00	9.60	12.30	5.20	9.85	12.50
L-Hydroxyproline	—	—	5.04	9.63	12.36	5.40	9.92	12.60
L-Proline	—	—	5.15	9.72	12.40	5.53	10.00	12.65
L-Histidine	—	—	6.53	12.40	14.32	6.69	12.20	14.51
Vitamin B ₆	1.72	2.93	—	—	—	—	—	—

tyrosine, Y = vitamin B₆ for Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} are given in Table 1 and Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. The values of stability constants are given in Tables 2 and 3.

The comparison of stability constants is given by the following equation,

$$\log k_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 [\log \beta_{20} + \log \beta_{02}],$$

the values of log k_m are 0.103, 0.089, -0.229, -0.257, -0.256, -0.464, -0.315 and 0.137 for Cd^{II} and -1.30, -1.21,

-1.13, -1.12, -1.06, -0.88, -0.79 and -0.78 for Zn^{II} for the systems [M-L-tyr.-vit.B₆], [M-L-arg.-vit.B₆], [M-L-met.-vit.B₆], [M-L-hyd.trp.-vit.B₆], [M-L-trp.-vit.B₆], [M-L-hyd.pro.-vit.B₆], [M-L-pro.-vit.B₆] and [M-L-his.-vit.B₆] (where M = Cd or Zn) systems respectively. The positive values of log k_m indicate that ternary complexes are more stable than binary complexes while the negative values indicates that binary complexes are more stable than ternary complexes⁸.

In case of L-tyrosine, α -amino and carboxylic groups took part in complex formation, the phenylhydroxyl groups not being involved in complex formation under the experimental conditions⁹. The lesser stability of the L-tyrosine complexes than the L-argininate complexes may be due to the presence of heavy benzene ring in L-tyrosine molecule.

The presence of distart NH_2 and guanidine groups in L-arginine¹⁰ causes still large asymmetry and hence a large shift in $E_{1/2}$ values than L-tyrosine. It also makes bond with the metal ion through amino and carboxylic groups, and the lesser stability of L-arginine complexes than L-methionine complexes is due to the fact that long chain L-arginine molecule is folded in such a way that its positively charged $=\text{NH}_2^+$ group comes adjacent to its α -amino group and therefore, metal cation is repelled by the adjacent positive charge resulting in lesser stability of its complexes than L-methionine complexes¹¹. In L-methionine, the reactive $-\text{S}-$ group does not participate in complex formation¹² and only α -amino and carboxylic groups are involved in complex formation.

L-Hydroxytryptophane and L-tryptophane coordinate to the metal ion through α -amino and carboxylic groups but there is a possibility of hydrogen-bonding between the indolic NH and $=\text{O}$ of the carboxylic group¹³ which can ef-

Fig.2. Zinc-L-tyrosinate-vitamin B₆ system.

fect the stability of their complexes. In L-hydroxyproline and L-proline, the α -imino groups take part in coordination¹⁴ and are responsible for the higher stability of their complexes than the other L-amino acids. In L-histidine, the amino nitrogen and imidazole nitrogen are involved in complex formation making six-membered ring and imidazole ring. The complex chelated with the imidazole nitrogen is the most stable one and this is the reason why L-histidine complexes have the maximum stability among the L-amino acids complexes. In vitamin B₆, there is a possibility of nitrogen to take part in coordination with the metal ion.

The sequence of stability constants of complexes with respect to metal ion is $\text{Cd}^{\text{II}} < \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, which is in accordance

with their ionic sizes¹⁵, while with the ligands, it is L-tyrosine $<$ L-arginine $<$ L-methionine $<$ L-hydroxytryptophane $<$ L-tryptophane $<$ L-hydroxyproline $<$ L-proline $<$ L-histidine which is in accordance with the nature of bonding between the metal and ligands, basicity of the ligands and steric hindrance.

Experimental

All the solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. Solution of Cd^{II} was prepared by dissolving $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (B.D.H.) and that of Zn^{II} by dissolving $\text{Zn}(\text{CO}_3)_2$ (Glaxo) in minimum quantity of HClO_4 . The excess acid was removed by heating. The concentration of metal ion in the test solution was 0.5 mM. The purity of L-amino acids was checked by chromatographic method¹⁶ and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled water.

Current-voltage measurements were made on a manual polarograph using a Toshniwal Polyflex PL-50 galvanometer. The capillary characteristics were $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.40 \text{ mg s}^{-1/2}$ at 60.02 cm (calculated) effective height of mercury³. Hydrogen gas was passed through each test solution before recording the C-V data. An Elico LI-120 pH-meter was used to measure the pH of the test solutions at 8.50 ± 0.01 adjusted with the dilute solutions of NaOH or HClO_4 as required. The entire study was carried at 25°.

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